

Effect of xylan on the mechanical performance of softwood kraft pulp 2D papers and 3D foams

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ABSTRACT: Pulp fibers are paramount in paper products and have lately seen emerging use in fiber foams. Xylan, an integral component in pulp fibers, is known to contribute to paper strength, but its effect on the strength of pulp fiber foams remains less explored.

In this study, we investigate the role of xylan in both 2D handsheets and 3D foams. For a softwood kraft pulp, we enzymatically removed 1% from pulp fibers and added 3% xylan to them by adsorption, corresponding to approximately a decrease of a tenth and an increase of a third of the total xylan content. The mechanical properties of 2D fiber networks, i.e., handsheets, made using the xylan-enriched pulp improved, particularly regarding tensile strength and Young's modulus; however, the decrease in mechanical properties of handsheets made from enzymatically-treated xylan-depleted pulp was more pronounced. In 3D networks – pulp fiber foams, much less fiber-fiber contacts formed, and thus the mechanical properties were not as much influenced by removal of xylan. Furthermore, the presence of the required surfactant on the fibers, acting as debonding agent, overshadows any positive effect xylan might have on fiber-fiber bonding. We propose that the improved mechanical properties for the sheets result from a combination of an increased number of fiber-fiber bonds and higher sheet density, while the deterioration in mechanical properties of handsheets comprising enzymatically-treated fibers is caused by the opposite effect.

Application: The findings here help the paper and pulp industry to understand how xylan content influences the mechanical properties of pulp fiber products, enabling tuning of material performance by altering the xylan content.

Xylan has frequently been demonstrated to increase the tensile strength and tensile stiffness of paper networks [1,2]. The amount of xylan on the fiber surface has been shown to correlate with Scott bond values, which characterize the energy required to rupture paper, while tensile strength is influenced by the total xylan content [3]. The adsorption of xylan on fiber surfaces is generally acknowledged to improve the mechanical properties of paper by strengthening fiber-fiber bonding, which is accompanied by an increase in swelling capacity owing to the higher surface charge and higher flexibility compared to regenerated cellulose fibers. As a result, xylan acts as a glue that increases the density of paper sheets and thus improves the paper's mechanical properties [4-6]. Foam formed fiber three-dimensional (3D) networks typically generate randomized dry fiber networks as pulp fibers entangle in an orthotropic manner. Under compression load, their network strength depends on the load carrying capacity of the fibers to withstand bending or sudden buckling, which causes the 3D network to collapse. In two-dimensional (2D) networks, the main failure mode in compression is buckling, which is happening when bending of the free fiber segments becomes too large [7], as well as by fiber-to-

fiber bond failures [8]. The strength of pulp fiber foams mainly depends on their network density, the frequency of fiber-fiber crossings, fiber-fiber cross-section area, and the mean fiber segment length. Increasing the bonded-area shortens the span length between fiber-fiber crossings and delays the onset of fiber buckling [9,10]. The influence of hemicelluloses on the mechanical properties of 3D fiber structures, such as fiber foams, is still not as established.

In order to identify the role of xylan in 2D and 3D fiber networks, we adjusted the xylan content of refined elemental chlorine free (ECF) bleached softwood kraft pulp (BSKP) by partially degrading xylan using an endo- β -xylanase or by increasing its content by adsorbing beechwood xylan on pulp fibers with two different refining degrees, 25 °SR and 50 °SR. The fibers were then formed into 2D sheets and 3D foams and characterized to elucidate their properties, focusing on the mechanical properties. The hypothesis was that the same fundamentals govern the mechanisms of strength in the 2D and 3D networks. We highlight the change in mechanical response of 2D to 3D fiber networks in compression and tensile testing and demonstrate how the xylan content on the pulp fibers correlates with mechanical properties. To further understand the location of

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xylan on the fibers and gain further insights into the pulp fiber surface properties, the surface energy of fibers and handsheets was measured.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Dried ECF fully bleached softwood kraft pulp (BSKP; 85% spruce, 10% pine, 5% larch) was kindly provided by Zellstoff Pöls AG (Pöls, Austria), having an ISO brightness of 88% and a lignin content below 0.15%. Beechwood xylan with 11% glucuronic acid *O*-methyl (MeGlcA) substitution (monosaccharide composition xylose:glucuronic-acid:other monosaccharides = 86.1:11.3:2.6; purity > 95%; molecular mass: M_n 18.5 kDa, M_w 23.8 kDa, M_w/M_n 1.3) [11] and endo-1,4- β -D-xylanase from *Neocallimastix patriciarium* (UNI-PROT accession no. P29127; GH11) were purchased from Megazyme International (Bray, Ireland). The BSKP was refined for 45 min (to 25 °SR) or 85 min (to 50 °SR) in a Valley beater according to ISO 5264-1:1979 “Pulps — Laboratory beating — Part 1: Valley beater method” at a consistency of 1.57 wt%.

Enzymatic degradation and xylan adsorption

Enzymatic treatment was performed at 50°C and pH 6 using 1 mL of endo-xylanase stock solution (10 000 U/mL). Adsorption was achieved adding beechwood xylan in 1 M sodium hydroxide (NaOH) at a concentration of 50 mg/mL to the fiber suspension and adjusting the pH to 7 using 1 M sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄). For both experiments, a corresponding blank was produced. The procedures are described in detail in Schaubeder et al. [12].

Carbohydrate analysis

Carbohydrate composition was determined via acid hydrolysis [13,14] using high performance anion exchange chromatography (HPAEC). After the adsorption experiments, the pulp suspension was filtered. The amount of adsorbed xylan was then calculated by measuring the refractive index of the filtrate and subtracting the xylan concentration determined using a calibration curve from the original xylan concentration. The amount of adsorbed xylan is equal to the amount of original xylan minus the amount of xylan in the filtrate. Since xylan precipitates at pH 7, the filtrate was diluted 1:1 with 1 M NaOH and dissolved. The calibration curve was determined in the same manner. Samples were taken after 15, 30, 60, and 120 min to obtain adsorption curves. The total surface charge of the fibers was determined by polyelectrolyte titration using a charge analyzing system (AFG Analytic GmbH; Leipzig, Germany).

Handsheet properties

The handsheet formation and properties were determined as follows:

- Drainability of the pulp suspension was determined according to the Schopper-Riegler (SR) method using

ISO 5267-1:1999 “Pulps — Determination of drainability — Part 1: Schopper-Riegler method.”

- Pulp disintegration: All pulps were disintegrated according to ISO 5263-1:2004 “Pulps — Laboratory wet disintegration — Part 1: Disintegration of chemical pulps.”
- Handsheet formation: Handsheets (80 g/m²) were formed on a Rapid-Köthen sheet former (Frank PTI; Birkenau, Germany) according to ISO 5269-2:2004 “Pulps — Preparation of laboratory sheets for physical testing — Part 2: Rapid-Köthen method.”
- Handsheet conditioning: Prior to testing, all handsheets were conditioned as described in ISO 187:2022 “Paper, board and pulps — Standard atmosphere for conditioning and testing and procedure for monitoring the atmosphere and conditioning of samples.”
- Thickness and apparent sheet density were determined according to ISO 534:2011 “Paper and board — Determination of thickness, density and specific volume”.
- Tensile properties were determined following ISO 1924-2:2008 “Paper and board — Determination of tensile properties — Part 2: Constant rate of elongation method (20 mm/min)” using a Frank PTI tensile tester.
- Short-span compression (SCT) strength was determined according to ISO 9895:2008 “Paper and board — Compressive strength — Short-span test.”
- Scott bond internal bond strength was determined following ISO 16260:2016 “Paper and board — Determination of internal bond strength.”

Foam preparation

The foams were prepared by frothing a pulp fiber suspension containing 0.1 wt% sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) from Sigma Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA) and 0.5 wt% carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) from Sigma Aldrich. Foamability experiments were performed using a hand-held mixer (Braun; Kronberg, Germany). Fiber suspensions were diluted to 7 wt% of solid fiber content and combined with SDS and CMC. Foam volumes were marked every 30 s, and the exact volumes were measured with water and a measuring cylinder. Each measurement was performed in triplicates. Air was introduced until the desired volume was reached, resulting in a density of 100 ± 5 kg·m⁻³. The wet foam was oven dried at 80°C until the moisture content was below 10%.

Foam properties

Compression tests were conducted using a Model 5969 universal mechanical tester from Instron (Norwood, MA, USA) equipped with a 1 kN load cell and a crosshead speed of 1.5 mm/min. Cylindrical foam specimens with a diameter of 25 mm and a height of 15 mm were compressed along the cylindrical axis according to ISO 844:2021 “Rigid cel-

	Arabinose	Rhamnose	Galactose	Glucose	Xylose	Mannose	Glucomanan	Cellulose	Xylan
blank _E	0.6	0.0	0.3	82.8	9.6	6.8	8.9	80.9	9.6
E	0.5	0.0	0.3	83.7	8.5	7.0	9.3	81.6	8.5
blank _X	0.6	0.0	0.3	82.4	9.9	6.9	9.2	80.4	9.9
X	0.5	0.0	0.3	79.7	12.9	6.7	8.8	77.8	12.9
Beechwood xylan	0.5	0.0	1.3	1.0	97.1	0.0	1.3	1.0	97.1

I. Monosaccharide contents of commercially available beechwood xylan and all pulps determined by HPLC [19]. All values are given in wt%.

lular plastics — Determination of compression properties.”

Tensile strength and strain at failure were determined using z-directional tensile tests. Cylindrical foam specimens with a diameter of 25 mm and a height of 15 mm were attached to plate grips with double-sided tape. To ensure adhesion to the test platens, the sample was compressed with a load of 15 N for 20 s and then tested at a strain of 80 mm/min. At least five samples were measured per foam formulation.

Dynamic vapor sorption (DVS) measurements were performed in triplicates using a DVS-Resolution (Surface Measurement Systems; London). For each measurement, isotherms were recorded from 0% relative humidity (RH) to 95% RH, with a step increment of 5% RH.

Inverse gas chromatography

Inverse gas chromatography (iGC) was used to assess the surface free energy γ^T and its distribution for fibers and handsheets. All experiments were performed using an iGC-Surface Energy Analyzer (SEA iGC; Surface Measurement Systems) equipped with a flame-ionization detector. Prior to measurements, samples were placed into silanized glass columns with a 4-mm inner diameter. Helium served as carrier gas, and methane was used to determine the column's dead volume. To determine γ^T , adsorption isotherms of non-polar alkanes (n-heptane, n-octane, n-nonane, and n-decane from Sigma Aldrich) were obtained at 30°C and 0% RH. Polar interactions were assessed using ethyl acetate (Honeywell; Charlotte, NC, USA), dichloromethane (Sigma Aldrich), ethanol (Merck; Rahway, NJ, USA), acetone, and acetonitrile (Sigma Aldrich). Retention times and volumes were analyzed with surface energy analysis software (Advanced 1.5) using the method after Dorris and Gray [15]. Each measurement was conducted twice.

Scanning electron microscopy

To examine the morphology of the papers, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were captured using a Tes-

can Vega 3 (Brno, Czech Republic) at an acceleration voltage of 1.5 kV with a secondary electron detector. Before the measurement, the samples were coated with a thin layer of gold using a Leica EM ACE200 (Wetzlar, Germany) sputter coater for 60 s at 50 mA.

To investigate the dry foam morphology, SEM micrographs (JCM-6000, JEOL; Tokyo) were taken at an acceleration voltage of 10 kV using a secondary electron detector. Prior to imaging, all samples were fixed with carbon tape to a sample holder and gold-coated using a sputter coater (JEOL Fine Coater JFC-1200) for 40 s at 30 mA.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Adjusting the fiber xylan content

The monosaccharide analysis (**Table I**) revealed that the enzymatic treatment reduced the total xylan content on the fibers by around 1% (from 9.6% to 8.5%), which corresponds to a reduction of the total xylan content in the fibers by about one tenth. The fibers prior to the enzymatic treatment are referred to as **blank_E** (blank for enzymatic degradation), and the enzymatically treated are denoted **E** (enzymatically treated pulp). Moreover, xylan content after xylan adsorption increased by 3% (from 9.9% to 12.9%) as shown in **Table I**, corresponding to a one-third increase in total xylan content on the fibers. Since the adsorption of xylan took place under alkaline/acidic conditions, another blank was prepared, referred to as **blank_X** (blank for xylan adsorption), that is contrasted to the xylan-enriched pulp denoted with **X**. With the resulting four different pulps (**blank_E**, **E**, **blank_X**, and **X**), both handsheets and foams were produced.

The amount of adsorbed xylan to the pulp was also confirmed using refractive index measurements. **Figure 1** shows the time-dependent average amount of xylan adsorbed on BSKP refined to 25 °SR or 50 °SR. The standard error of mean is significantly higher for BSKP refined to 50 °SR, which is related to more fines being present, affecting the measured refractive indices. Thus, this alternative

1. Time dependent xylan adsorption on bleached softwood kraft pulp (BSKP) refined to 25 °SR (red) and 50 °SR (grey) determined by refractive index measurements (circles). The error bars are standard errors of mean. Squares show the adsorbed amount of xylan determined by monosaccharide analysis.

method to determine the adsorbed amount of xylan is more suitable for pulps with a low-to-medium degree of refining. The average values for xylan adsorption determined by monosaccharide analysis (average of two samples for 50 °SR, and average of five samples for 25 °SR) are within the standard errors of mean (represented as squares in Fig. 1), but in both cases, they are slightly lower than the amounts determined by the refractive index method.

Surface energy of xylan adjusted pulp fibers and handsheets

We determined the surface energy of the xylan modified fibers and handsheets to define the effect of the amount of xylan on pulp fiber surface properties. In general, surfaces of natural fibers are heterogeneous [16,17]. In comparison to the **blank_E** and **blank_X**, the total surface energy γ^T of the modified pulp fibers **E** and **X** had broader distributions. The broadened distribution of γ^T of **X** (Fig. 2a) after adsorption of xylan indicates that xylan adsorbed heterogeneously on the fibers. Xylan likely adsorbs on higher surface energy sites of the fibers, causing the shift to lower γ^T . For handsheets comprising the same fibers, we observed an upward shift of γ^T . Handsheets comprise a 2D fiber network of bonded fibers, and it seems that agglomerated amorphous xylan that facilitates fiber bonding is concentrated in bonded areas, exposing pure cellulose that results in the shift to higher surface energies (Fig. 2b). These observations are in accordance with Nypelö et al. [18], who noticed a decrease in surface energy by the addition of xylan to pulp fibers. Baltazar-y-Jimenez and Bismarck [19] reported that surface energy of natural fibers increased linearly with cellulose content of the fibers. A broadening of the surface energy distributions observed for enzymatical-

ly-treated pulp fibers **E** after handsheet making when compared to xylan-treated fibers could be attributed to the formation of fiber-fiber contacts predominantly at xylan rich sites, thus the fiber surfaces exposed in handsheets are cellulose rich, leading to an increased surface energy. In the case of **X**, the addition of xylan should be on the fiber surface, hence resulting in shifts to lower γ^T . However, in handsheets, we again observed an upward shift of the surface energy, again indicating that xylan might be involved in fiber-fiber bonds or joints.

Foaming of pulp fiber suspensions with adjusted xylan contents and properties of fiber foams

The foamability of pulp fibers with varying xylan contents was investigated (Fig. 3). Wet foams comprising fibers with higher xylan content led to higher foaming rates and the largest total foam volume. Only small differences in foaming rate and height were observed between **blank_E** and **blank_X**, though the foam height of **E** plateaued after 1 min of mixing. Xylan promotes foaming rates and correlates with the maximum produced foam height. The enhanced foamability suggests that an increasing fiber surface charge – introduced by a higher number of xylan aggregates on the fiber surface – increases the electrostatic repulsion between SDS and CMC, leading to better bubble stabilization. With the increase of MeGlcA content on the pulp fibers, an increase in the total fiber surface charge could be confirmed. The total surface charge of the pulp increased by 64% after xylan adsorption (from **blank_X**: 53 ± 5 mmol/kg to **X**: 87 ± 5 mmol/kg) [12], while the degradation of 1% xylan resulted in a decrease in total surface charge of only 15% (from **blank_E**: 54 ± 6 mmol/kg to **E**: 46 ± 5 mmol/kg)

2. Total surface energy distribution plotted against the percentage of surface area increment of (a) fibers and (b) handsheets. The distributions are derived by integration of the surface energy profiles, displaying the percentage increase in area increment against the surface energy.

3. Foam volume of softwood blank_E, E, blank_X, and X pulp fiber suspensions, containing 0.1 wt% sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) and 0.5 wt% carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) as a function of frothing time.

[12]. The stronger repulsion between the fibers separated them, promoting a more uniform distribution of bubbles and better stabilization by the fibers.

Mechanical properties of 2D and 3D pulp products

We have previously reported that the xylan content has a significant impact on the mechanical properties of handsheets [12]. In particular, the handsheet density is important for strength. While all sheets exhibited similar thicknesses between 122 and 128 μm , the density decreased

by 1.7% after enzymatic degradation (from **blank_E**: $0.642 \pm 0.005 \text{ g/cm}^3$ to **E**: $0.631 \pm 0.003 \text{ g/cm}^3$) and increased by 2% after xylan adsorption (from **blank_X**: $0.642 \pm 0.003 \text{ g/cm}^3$ to **X**: $0.655 \pm 0.004 \text{ g/cm}^3$), indicating that the adsorption of xylan leads to an increase in bonded fiber area that results in increased handsheet density [12]. These seemingly small changes do have a significant impact on the mechanical properties; the internal bond strength (**Fig. 4a**) correlates well with the xylan content. A decrease of 12% was observed after xylan degradation (from **blank_E**: $53.8 \pm 0.3 \text{ J/m}^2$ to **E**: $47.4 \pm 0.4 \text{ J/m}^2$), while an

4. Bond strength and compressive properties of handsheets and foams: (a) internal bond strength; (b) short-span compression strength of handsheets [12]; and (c) compressive modulus and strength of foams compared with the corresponding xylan content of the pulp fibers.

increase of 16% was determined after xylan adsorption (from **blank_X**: 59.1 ± 0.5 J/m² to **X**: 68.5 ± 0.4 J/m²), indicating a higher bond strength between the fibers with increasing xylan content [12].

The mechanical properties of foam networks are commonly characterized by testing their resistance to compression loads. Compression tests showed that a total decrease of 1% xylan on the pulp fibers does not significantly affect the Young's modulus of the pulp fiber foams but rather the overall strength (Fig. 4c). In contrast, both the modulus and compression strength slightly increased upon addition of xylan (from **blank_X**: 0.16 ± 0.02 MPa to **X**: 0.22 ± 0.02 MPa). The short-span compression strength tests of handsheets followed this trend (Fig. 4b); it decreased by 3% after enzymatic xylan removal (from **blank_E**: 2.08 ± 0.03 kN/m to **E**: 2.01 ± 0.03 kN/m), while increasing by 6% after xylan adsorption (from **blank_X**: 2.19 ± 0.04 kN/m to **X**: 2.32 ± 0.05 kN/m), which can be explained by the change in handsheet density.

The tensile properties of handsheets (**Fig. 5a**) and of

pulp fiber foams in z-direction (Fig. 5c) show distinct changes in fibrous 2D and 3D systems. In 2D, the tensile index decreased by 8% after enzymatic degradation of 1% xylan (from **blank_E**: 64.4 ± 0.8 Nm/g to **E**: 59.3 ± 0.6 Nm/g), while it increased by 9% after adsorption of 3% xylan, (from **blank_X**: 70.3 ± 1.2 Nm/g to **X**: 76.3 ± 1.7 Nm/g) [12]. It is speculated that this small difference in absolute numbers is due to the presence of adsorbed xylan aggregates, which are less effective in increasing the bond strength compared to xylan present in the internal fiber layers. The Young's moduli (Fig. 5b) showed a similar trend, with a 4% decrease after degradation (from **blank_E**: 5.0 ± 0.1 GPa to **E**: 4.8 ± 0.1 GPa) and a 8% increase after adsorption (from **blank_X**: 5.2 ± 0.1 GPa to **X**: 5.6 ± 0.1 GPa) [12]. However, in 3D foam structures, tensile strength remained unaffected, with no significant correlation between xylan content and tensile properties. The maximum z-tensile strength (Fig. 5c) of the foams with varying xylan contents was within the same range, albeit with large standard deviations. In all cases, the fracture occurred in re-

5. Tensile properties of handsheets and foams: (a) tensile index of handsheets; (b) Young's moduli of handsheets [12]; and (c) tensile strength of foams compared with the corresponding xylan content of the pulp fibers.

gions with the lowest foam density, which may be attributed to the inhomogeneous fiber arrangement caused by foam making and forming. To determine the significance of the differences between the values, an ANOVA test was conducted, showing that foams **E** and **X** did not significantly differ from each other. In contrast to the compression moduli, no correlation between the tensile strength and the xylan content on pulp fibers present in the foams could be observed. Pulp fiber foams have a much lower density when compared to handsheets and thus significantly lower mechanical properties. The number and strength of fiber-fiber contacts, i.e., crossing points, affects the lateral support of fibers in compression, determining overall mechanical properties of pulp fiber foams [20]. Pulp fiber foams produced from fiber suspensions containing only SDS as foaming agent have much lower mechanical properties compared to pulp fiber foams made from froths containing SDS and CMC (or other polymer additives, for that matter [10]), which acts both as viscosifier –

improving liquid froth stability – and bonding agent [20]. In our case, the presence of CMC in 3D networks seems to have a more profound effect on fiber-fiber bonding than removed or adsorbed xylan. Lappalainen et al. [21] reported that SDS does not affect handsheet tensile index but significantly lowers Scott bond (delamination energy). This was attributed to the foam formed paper sheets containing “a significantly larger number of large pores” [21], and they thus concluded that SDS “is not a significant reason for the weaker strength properties of foam-formed paper samples” [21].

In water sorption measurements, the highest water uptake was observed for the foam with the highest xylan content (**Fig. 6**). Xylan is considered to be more hygroscopic than cellulose and that may lead to a higher susceptibility towards water [22], and therefore, the highest change in mass upon water sorption occurred in the sample with the highest xylan amount. The strength of cellulosic materials usually decreases with increasing moisture content in the

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6. Moisture absorption (DVS) in a humidity range from 25% to 95% RH at 25°C represented by the change of mass of blank_E, E, blank_X, and X.

network [23]. At 50% RH, which was the testing environment of the mechanical tests, **X** had the highest water content but had also the highest compression strength. This was taken as an indirect indication that xylan is a bonding agent in the interfiber contact areas, increasing the bond strength of fiber joints.

Morphology

Figure 7 shows SEM images of the handsheets. A higher proportion of fibrils are visible in **E** compared to **blank_E**, resulting from the enzymatic treatment, while at this magnification, no clear differences between **blank_X** and **X** are apparent.

The morphology of the foams having a density of 100 ± 5 kg/m³ was also investigated using SEM. In contrast to the handsheets, no structural change of the fibers or a difference in the 3D-network morphology could be observed in the micrographs (**Fig. 8**).

CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that xylan plays a crucial role in influencing the mechanical properties of both 2D papers and 3D pulp fiber foams. The primary distinction between the strengthening mechanisms in 2D and 3D networks are governed by fiber-fiber bonding. In handsheets, xylan significantly enhances mechanical properties by increasing their bonded area, which directly translates to improved strength and stiffness. In contrast, in 3D foams, the fiber-fiber interactions are fewer, and the effect of xylan is less pronounced, primarily contributing to foam formation and stability rather than improving strength. This suggests that in 3D net-

works, the physical arrangement and distribution of fibers dominate the mechanical properties, while in 2D networks, the increase in fiber-fiber bond strength plays the key role. **TJ**

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LITERATURE CITED

1. Danielsson, S. and Lindström, M.E., *Nord. Pulp Pap. Res. J.* 20(4): 436(2005). <https://doi.org/10.3183/npprj-2005-20-04-p436-441>.
2. Roberts, J.C., McCarthy, A.J., Flynn, N.J., et al., *Enzyme Microb. Technol.* 12(3): 210(1990). [https://doi.org/10.1016/0141-0229\(90\)90040-W](https://doi.org/10.1016/0141-0229(90)90040-W).
3. Schönberg, C., Oksanen, T., Suurnäkki, A., et al., *Holzforchung* 55(6): 639(2001). <https://doi.org/10.1515/HF.2001.104>.
4. Miletzky, A., Fischer, W.J., Czibula, C., et al., *Cellulose* 22: 849(2015). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10570-014-0532-8>.
5. Pettersson, S.E. and Rydholm, S.A., *Sven. Papperstidn.* 64(Part 3): 4(1961).
6. Laine, J., Hynynen, R., and Stenius, P., "The effect of surface chemical composition and charge on the fiber and paper properties of unbleached and bleached kraft pulps," in *The Fundamentals of Papermaking Materials, Trans. of the Xlth Fund. Res. Symp. Cambridge, 1997* (C.F. Baker, Ed.), FRC, Manchester, 2018, pp. 859–892. <https://doi.org/10.15376/frc.1997.2.859>.
7. Brandberg, A. and Kulachenko, A., *Cellulose* 27: 6065(2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10570-020-03153-2>.

7. Handsheet structure. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images with a magnification of 400x: (a) blank_E, (b) E, (c) blank_X, and (d) X, as recorded with a secondary electron detector.

8. Characteristic SEM micrographs representing the foam structure, with a magnification of 300x: (a) blank_E, (b) E, (c) blank_X, and (d) X pulp fiber foams.

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8. Perkins, J. and McEvoy, R.P., *Tappi* 64(2): 99(1981).
9. Ketoja, J.A., Paunonen, S., Jetsu, P., et al., *Materials* 12(3): 384(2019). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma12030384>.
10. Pöhler, T., Ketoja, J.A., Lappalainen, T., et al., *Cellulose* 27: 6961(2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10570-020-03263-x>.
11. Palasingh, C., Nakayama, K., Abik, F., et al., *Carbohydr. Polym.* 292: 119660(2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2022.119660>.
12. Schaubeder, J.B., Spirk, S., Fliri, L., et al., *Carbohydr. Polym.* 323: 121371(2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2023.121371>.
13. Theander, O. and Westerlund, E.A., *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 34(2): 330(1986). <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf00068a045>.
14. Wojtasz-Mucha, J., Hasani, M., and Theliander, H., *Bioresour. Technol.* 241: 120(2017). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2017.05.061>.
15. Dorris, G.M. and Gray, D.G., *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 77(2): 353(1982). [https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9797\(80\)90304-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9797(80)90304-5).
16. Zafeiropoulos, N.E., Vickers, P.E., Baillie, C.A., et al., *J. Mater. Sci.* 38: 3903(2003). <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1026133826672>.
17. Williams, T., Hosur, M., Theodore, M., et al., *Int. J. Polym. Sci.* 1(2011). <https://doi.org/10.1155/2011/192865>.
18. Nypelö, T., Asaadi, S., Kneidinger, G., et al., *Cellulose* 25: 5297(2018). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10570-018-1902-4>.
19. Baltazar-y-Jimenez, A. and Bismarck, A., *Cellulose* 14: 115(2007). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10570-006-9092-x>.
20. Wagner, M., Biegler, V., Wurm, S., et al., *Composites, Part A* 188: 108515(2025). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2024.108515>.
21. Lappalainen, T., Salminen, K., Kinnunen, K., et al., *Nord. Pulp Pap. Res. J.* 29(4): 689(2014). <https://doi.org/10.3183/npprj-2014-29-04-p689-699>.
22. Pääkkönen, T., Dimic-Misic, K., Orelma, H., et al., *Cellulose* 23: 277(2016). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10570-015-0824-7>.
23. Salmén, L. and Olsson, A.-M., *Wood Sci. Technol.* 50: 81(2016). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00226-015-0777-x>.

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ABOUT THE AUTHORS

We chose to investigate the role of xylan in fiber networks because of its known significance in enhancing the mechanical properties of pulp-based materials that are used extensively in the paper and packaging industries. However, its role in newer applications, such as 3D fiber foams, remains largely unexplored. By understanding how xylan content influences both 2D paper sheets and 3D foam structures, we aim to provide new insights that could lead to the targeted development of stronger, more versatile, and sustainable fiber-based products.

Previous research focused mainly on understanding xylan's effects in conventional 2D fiber networks like paper and board. This study is a first attempt to extend that work by investigating xylan's role in the mechanical performance of 3D fiber foams, which have a much lower density and different structural characteristics. While other studies have also shown that xylan improves fiber-fiber bonding in 2D networks, our research highlights the challenges and behaviors of xylan in 3D structures, thereby trying to bridge a gap in the existing literature.

The most challenging aspect of this study was achieving a controlled and uniform modification of xylan content in the fiber networks without altering other fiber properties. We tried to address this by using precise enzymatic degradation and adsorption techniques, along with careful monitoring of xylan content through advanced analytical methods.

We discovered that xylan seems to play fundamentally different roles, depending on the dimensionality of the fiber network. While it is known to enhance the mechanical properties of 2D sheets by reinforcing fiber-fiber bonds, it contributes less to mechanical strength in 3D foams, but is helping in foam formation and stability. While these findings were partly to be expected, they also indicate that more research regarding the interplay of the effect of xylan and the structural arrangement within fiber networks is required.

Although we anticipated that xylan would have a less significant effect in 3D foams compared to 2D sheets due to the lower network density, we were surprised by how little influence it actually had, particularly in xylan-depleted fibers. Even with a significant reduction in xylan content, the mechanical properties of the foams did not change substantially. This finding partly challenges the conventional understanding of xylan as a general strength-enhancing component and suggests that its contribution is highly dependent on the structural properties of the fiber network.

Mills can use the information here to better tailor the xylan content in their pulp processing to optimize product performance based on specific applications, such as stronger paper sheets. Understanding the differential effects of xylan in 2D and 3D struc-

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tures should enable a more precise control over the final product properties.

The next step in this research is to explore the influence of different hemicelluloses and their combination in 3D fiber networks to identify optimal formulations for high-performance materials. Additionally, studying xylan's interaction with other strength-enhancing additives should help further improve the mechanical properties of fiber-based products.

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